

EFFECTIVENESS OF PRIVATE STAKEHOLDERS IN COMPETITION TOWARDS NATIONAL GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT IN TANZANIA - CASE STUDY MOSHI MUNICIPALITY

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ABSTRACT: This study focused on the Effectiveness of private stakeholders in competition towards nation growth and development in Moshi Municipal. The study used mixed research design, cross sectional survey design because it provided opportunity to collect data from different type of participants as well as measuring different variables in the population of interest at a single point of time and Case study was used in this study because is a very popular form of qualitative analysis and involves a careful and complete observation of a social unit. The main objective of the study was to examine the effectiveness of private stakeholders in competition towards nation growth and development in Tanzania. The research methodology was designed to collect data from the 100 respondents where by different tools was used including the questionnaires, interviews and documentary. The collected data from the study was statistically analyzed in the descriptive analysis by the help of Microsoft excel and Statistical Package for social science.

The findings revealed that effectiveness of stakeholders in competition includes the following, stimulate globalization,

Develop and maintain infrastructures and services, Promote and expand existing businesses as well as Building better business enabling environments and Address inefficiency in the local economy.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Problem

Sustainable development meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. The economy is not sufficiently diversified away from the oil and gas sector. It needs to move into knowledge-based industries, which employ more people than the oil and gas sector. Loveridge & Wilson (2017), public-private partnership is an umbrella term for the increasingly systematic and strategic efforts of development organizations to work with business to achieve development results

The economic development in many developing countries has deteriorated in recent years. Between 2010 and 2014, aggregate GDP expanded at an average pace of 6.0%, but growth slowed to an average of 4.2% between 2015 and 2018. The slowdown in growth has been particularly pronounced in Africa, Latin America and Western Asia. In 2019, average GDP growth in developing countries could fall below 4.0%, amid lingering fragilities in Argentina, Brazil and South Africa, and weaker economic conditions in Mexico, Saudi Arabia and Turkey (United Nations, 2019).

Nigeria is one of the largest countries in Africa, with an estimated population of about 158 million (World Bank, 2010). Agriculture was the mainstay of the Nigerian economy before the discovery, exploration and exportation of oil and over dependence on its revenue for economic expenditure. Despite the fact that Nigeria is buoyantly endowed with agricultural and other natural resources, the agricultural sector is still growing at a very slow rate. This is leading to problems including unemployment, failure of industrial due to lack of raw materials.

The economy of Kenya is continuing to be the largest in the East African region and third largest in Sub - Saharan Africa after South Africa and Nigeria respectively. At present Kenya is one of the most highly literate countries in sub - Saharan Africa. But more than 60% people of Kenya live below the poverty line. Rapid increases in

inflation could reduce economic growth and worsen the poverty levels of the citizens of Kenya. Economic development is dependent on agricultural improvement. Kenya is the largest food and agricultural products importer in east Africa. About 82% of the total land in Kenya is classified as arid and semi-arid. Agricultural products depend on proper rainfall. Staple food of Kenya is maize, which accounted about 65% of total staple food caloric intake and 36% of total food caloric intake (Mohojan, 2013).

The government's Development Vision 2025 strategy, focuses on the private sector, prioritizes industrialization and job creation and seems intended to promote good governance. Tanzania has one of fastest growing economies with nearly 7 percent annual national GDP growth since 2000. Yet, widespread poverty persists with 49% of Tanzania's population living below the international extreme poverty line of \$1.90 per day (World Bank, 2011). Tanzania's predominantly rural population by 73%, economic growth has been limited. Inclusive, broad-based growth is hindered by low productivity growth in labor intensive sectors like agriculture, which employs 77% of working age adults. The agriculture sector grew just 4 percent per year over the past decade.

The government recognizes the role of private sector in bringing about socio-economic development through investments. Public- Private Partnership (PPP) provides important instrument for attracting investments. PPPs can enable the government to fulfill its responsibilities in efficient delivery of socio-economic goods and services by ensuring efficiency, effectiveness, accountability, quality and outreach of services. UNDP Tanzania (2012) reports that various stakeholders across sectors came together in a roundtable discussion to discuss the role of the private sector in poverty reduction. This makes the researcher of current study to investigate effectiveness of private stakeholders in competition towards nation growth and development in Tanzania. Case Study Moshi Municipality.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

Unless the Tanzanian economy becomes more productive and competitive in an increasingly global and liberalized market, the vision of high-quality livelihood is not tenable. Poverty is the normal condition of life for large numbers of Tanzanians, in both urban and rural areas. Access to social services continues to be unequally

distributed. African), Poverty and income inequality remain high despite high economic growth. Infrastructure bottlenecks are most notable in the transport and energy sectors.

One of the development challenges on the social front is youth unemployment, which increased to 7.3% in 2016, compared with 5.7% in 2012. Ministry of Industry, Trade and Investment (2016), the problems that constrain Tanzania's performance such as a cumbersome business environment characterized by limited access to land and high transaction costs from regulatory requirements in licensing, compliance and enforcement of a multiplicity of taxes, fees, charges and levies. Mwiru (2015), citizen involvement in decision making is very low and citizens are not aware of their rights, roles and responsibilities which caused by lack of citizenship education, miscommunication between leaders also many citizens vii being illiterate. Private sector engagement is an essential component of the economic development of Tanzania and the country's efforts to reach middle-income status. Therefore, the researcher aims to conduct this study to examine effectiveness of private stakeholders in competition towards nation growth and development in Tanzania. Case study Moshi Municipality.

1.3 Research Hypothesis

1. There is no significant influence of private stakeholders on national growth and development in Tanzania.
2. There are no significant competitions of private stakeholders in national growth and development in Tanzania.

1.4 Research Objectives

1.4.1 General Objective

The main objective is to examine the effectiveness of private stakeholders in competition towards nation growth and development in Tanzania. Case Study Moshi Municipality.

1.4.2 Specific Objectives

To assess involvement of private stakeholders in competition to enhancing national growth and development

1. To examine the extent to which private stakeholders affects national growth and development
2. To identify factors hinders private stakeholders in competition in enhancing national growth

1.4.3 Research Questions

The researcher of this study was guided by:-

1. How private stakeholders involve in competition in enhancing national growth and development?
2. To what extent do private stakeholders affect national growth and development?
3. Which factors hinders private stakeholders in competition in enhancing national growth and development?

1.5 Significance of the Study

This study was to determine the involvement of private stakeholders in competition to enhancing national growth and development. The information is very important to the government and policy makers for filling the policy gaps relating to national growth and development and in addressing the issue of private stakeholders. The findings of the study will help policy makers to critically examine the various possibilities of promoting economic growth and development in Tanzania with regards to the role of private stakeholders in economic growth and development.

The findings will provide the basis that economic growth and development in Tanzania should be supported by private stakeholders and that the success of plans and policies implemented in the sectors are depended on private sectors developments for their successful implementation.

The findings of the study are also important for understanding the factors hinders in competition in enhancing national growth and development source of problems, the study will provide information to the government institutions on factors hinders national growth and development in relationship to the competition of private stakeholders. The study will add to the literature by filling the knowledge gaps on the problems of private stakeholders and how the problem can possibly be addressed in the nation.

1.7 Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study was conducted in Kilimanjaro region specifically in Moshi municipality in which the data was collected from different private stakeholders namely businesspeople, investors industrial owners and banks where by the aim is to secure information as guided by objective of this study such as to examine the effectiveness of private stakeholders in competition towards nation growth and development in Tanzania

1.8 Theoretical Framework

Game Theory by Neumann, J. & Morgenstern, O. (1944)

A game is a situation in which two or more participants take part in pursuit of certain conflicting objectives. According to Li & Zhou (2015), Game theory is theory and method to study phenomenon with struggle or competitive features. Game Theory is the study of the ways in which interacting choices of economic agents produce outcomes with respect to the preferences (or utilities) of those agents, where the outcomes in question might have been intended by none of the agents.

It attempts to take into consideration the interactions between the participants and their behavior to study the strategic decision making between rational individuals. Carbone (2017), stakeholder engagement is a key aspect of community development world. It is assumed that players within the game are rational and strive to maximize their payoffs in the game. When examining games that are already set up, it is assumed on behalf that the payouts listed include the sum of all payoffs associated with that outcome.

Game theory is much more successful in some applications than others. The game theory can be applied to decide the best course in conflicting situations of private stakeholders in the nation. It provides a framework for competitor's reactions to the firm actions as well Game theory is a management device which helps rational decision-making. Sakir (2016), cooperative games among the citizens lead a poor country to become rich over time while non-cooperative games can make a developed country become poor over time.

1.9 Conceptual Framework

A conceptual framework illustrates that there is close relationship of national growth and development with the roles played by private stakeholders namely trade unions, employees, creditors, investors, communities, partners and suppliers also due to government policy of its taxation policy, spending, revenues politics and leadership.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1.1 Conceptual Framework

Source: Own construct (2020)

1.10 Operational Definitions of Key Terms

Competition means rivalry among private stakeholders where each stakeholder tries to increase sales, profits and market share by varying the marketing mix of price, product, distribution and promotion.

Effectiveness is the capability of private stakeholders to produce desired result or the ability to produce desired output in the firms.

Nation Growth is the increase in the inflation adjusted market value of the goods and services produced by an economy over time.

National Development is the ability of a county or countries to improve the social welfare of the people for example by providing quality education, potable water, transportation infrastructure and medical care.

Private Stakeholders are an investor in companies whose actions determine the outcome of business decisions.

LITERTURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

This chapter gives explanations about review of literature which consists of review of related theories, review of empirical studies and demonstration of knowledge gap.

2.1 Review of Related Theories

Total Quality Management (TQM)

Total Quality Management is one of the contemporary trends in organizational management, which is applicable to the management of private institutions towards national development and growth. It involves long-term dedication to improving of quality throughout the organization, and the active participation of all members at all levels to meet and exceed their customer's expectations i.e. parents, students, teachers, and the community. Sadikoglu (2014), the firms in face were lack of employee involvement, awareness and commitment of the employees, inappropriate firm structure, and lack of the resources.

Quality should be understood from the point of view of the customer's satisfaction rather than from the supplier's intentions. It over-emphasizes the importance of environment or context in which goals are set. It increases comparison between individuals at work place and as a result their work may lack innovation, creativity and sometimes becomes monotonous. Sadikoglu (2014), firms should improve employees' involvement/commitment/awareness to TQM, enhance firm structure, and provide resources to overcome the barriers that prevent effective implementation of TQM practices Therefore, relevance of this theory provides private stakeholders to adapt to appropriate strategies for effectively competition towards national growth and development.

Consumer's Involvement Theory (Sherif & Cantril, 1947)

Consumer Involvement Theory is the state of mind that motivates a consumer to make a purchase, or the importance a consumer places on a product or service. There are different levels of involvement a consumer can have in the decision-making process and different factors that influence that involvement. Nina & Sally (2008), involvement is an individual difference variable found to influence consumers' decision making and communication behaviors.

The theory is linked to this study involvement can be can be as a target of private stakeholder to influence consumers through advertisement of its products and services in order to purchase them which can enhance the development of industrial sectors than stimulate the growth of employment, improvement of citizens life standard and hence national growth and development.

2.3 Review of Empirical Studies

2.3.1 Involvement of Private Stakeholders in Competition to Growth and Development

Antonsen (2011) studied about the stakeholders' involvement in the process of building and maintaining a destination brand. The purpose was to explore how destination marketing organization creates and builds a strong destination brand and how the stakeholders have been involved in the process. The study found that a destination is a place that attracts visitors for a temporary stay to participate in tourism related activities or non-activities. Globalization, the increased number of travelers and the increased buying power have increased the competition between the destinations and the destinations have become more substitutable. It has been agreed that destinations can be branded as well as products and to be competitive it is getting common to brand destinations. Destination marketing organization is responsible for the marketing of an identifiable destination.

Kasawala (2013) did a study about perceptions of the Tanzanian community on public private partnership in the provision of health services: the case of CCBRT. The study investigated the perception of the Tanzanian community on Public Private Partnership (PPP) in the provision of health services in Tanzania, using

Comprehensive Community Based Rehabilitation in Tanzania (CCBRT) as a case study. Findings established that PPP concept is positively perceived by majority of respondents regardless of their occupations, education level, gender and age. However, people perceive wrongly concept of PPPs as for solely heavy investment projects, but PPP includes small projects as well like facilitating patient's referrals to hospitals for treatment. However bureaucratic practices during PPP implementation and poor interpersonal relations between clients and health staff were also found in the study. The study recommended that Tanzania should embrace more the use of the PPP concept as it gives wide choices of collaboration.

Halima, Alam & Sahazali (2014) carried out titled tourist's perceptions towards the role of stakeholders in sustainable Tourism. The purpose was to discover if differences in tourists' perceptions of sustainable tourism development in Melaka existed between three stakeholder groups: government, local residents and private entrepreneurs. The findings indicated that the government, private and local community has played a major role for satisfying the tourists' in shaping the development of sustainable tourism in Melaka. The study emphasizes on scale methods in analyzing and reviewing the role of government, private and local communities. To the distinct stakeholders' facilities, the majority of tourists generally were welcoming of sustainable tourism.

2.3.2 The Extent to which Private stakeholders Affects Growth and Development

Babatunde (2017) conducted a research titled Government spending on infrastructure and economic growth in Nigeria aimed at investigating government spending on infrastructure. Both primary and secondary data are used for the study. Findings from the study indicate that government spending on transport and communication, education and health infrastructure has significant effects on economic growth; spending on agriculture and natural resources infrastructure recorded a significant inverse effect on economic growth in Nigeria. An element of fiscal illusion was observed in the government spending on agriculture and natural resources indicating that government is not contributing as much as the private sector in spending on agriculture and natural resources infrastructure in Nigeria.

Alfred (2016) studied about the role of public private partnership in improved health care services for older people: the case of Morogoro Municipal council. The study aimed to study the role of PPP in improved healthcare services for older people in Morogoro Municipal Council. Using Case study, a number of 84 respondents were purposely involved in the study. The study revealed that the majority of the respondents (61.3%) were aware of the existing collaboration between government and private sectors in providing healthcare services. The study also found out that 69.4% of the respondents agreed that PPP has increased efficiency in health services delivery for older people. The study concluded by recommended to the central government to avoid bureaucracy and grant full decentralization of PPPs to all local government with authority to reach agreements with partners in provision of healthcare services especially for older people because with centralized PPP programs it is difficult for local government to exercise PPP.

Fillip kowska Wegrzyn (2019) studied about understanding of public–private partnership stakeholders as a condition of sustainable development. The study aimed to contribute to a theoretical understanding of the determinants of sustainable city development and PPP success factors. The research claims that the PPP procurement is consistent with sustainable urban development and the PPP model, accompanied by the stakeholder theory, requires evaluation which balances diverse stakeholders' interests along the triple bottom of sustainable development. Sustainable development shapes the procurement of infrastructure projects towards PPP, rather than a conventional form of sole public sector infrastructure delivery. PPP is a response to sustainable development pluralism as government and people (individuals and business), participating and engaged in PPP, are valuable human and social resources.

2.3.3 Factors Hinders Private Stakeholders in Competition in National Growth

OECD (2013) on overview of progress and policy challenges in Tanzania. The investment regime could be further rationalized through strengthening of the Tanzania Investment Centre as a one stop shop to have full mandate for approval of investment permits. Tanzania still lacks adequate enabling infrastructure and the private sector does not actively participate in infrastructure development. Access to

land can be a lengthy process for foreign and domestic investors alike, and land tenure remains insecure for smallholders. In addition, restrictions on agricultural trade hinder investment in agriculture. Informed by the subsequent chapters of this report, this overview provides policy options to address these challenges, in view of enabling Tanzania to attract higher investment and to potentially become a regional trade and investment hub.

Hamza (2013) on the assessment of challenges and prospects of capital markets development: a case study of Tanzania. The study was conducted at Dar Es Salaam City and involved a sample size of 80 respondents drawn from Top Managers and the personnel from the Dar Es Salaam Stock Exchange (DSE), the Capital Market and Securities Authority (CMSA), Brokerage Firms and Private Advocates, who were selected through random and purposive sampling techniques. The study revealed that there are challenges for the capital market development that remain unsolved since the establishment of the CMSA and the DSE, despite the prospects experienced to the market. Hence the study recommends for more reforms to our laws and policies governing the capital market business, demutualization of the DSE, Stock Markets integration so as to make the market flexible hence rapid development of the market.

Ibrahim (2013) also carried out a study about the private sector in post revolution Egypt found that the private sector in Egypt is a mix of micro, small to medium, and large enterprises. Microenterprises, employing one to four employees, comprise nearly 91 percent of all Egyptian enterprises. Small and medium enterprises, employing five to 100 people, comprise 8 percent, and large corporations constitute less than 1 percent of total Egyptian enterprises. Small and medium enterprises, which operate in the manufacturing and services sectors, face numerous obstacles, including limited access to financing, poor labor skills, inconsistent standards, and weak links to large firms. They lack effective representation in the existing private sector institutional framework, which is dominated by large firms. The study recommended developing a viable, concerted economic vision that may provide realistic policy recommendations on how to achieve market-driven and sustainable growth while increasing employment and social justice and expand existing efforts to include small and medium enterprises and reach out to stakeholders, such as labor unions.

2.4 Research Gap

Basing on the studies reviewed, it found that the national growth and development is highly associated not only to government itself. There are also influenced by the roles played by the private institutions. Despite that there is involvement of private stakeholders in the country, yet scholars did not show its implications on their contributions to national growth and development although there are positive contributions including employment opportunities to youths. Therefore, the study will be conducted to find out the effectiveness of private stakeholders in competition towards nation growth and development in Tanzania - Case Study Moshi Municipality

RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter contains research design, target population, description of sample and sampling techniques, description of data collection instrument, validity and reliability of research instrument, description of data collection and analysis procedure and ethical consideration.

3.2 Research Design

The research design is the conceptual structure within which research is conducted; it constitutes the blueprint for the collection, measurement and analysis of data (Kothari, 2004). The study used mixed research design. The study used cross sectional survey design because it provides opportunity to collect data from different type of participants as well as measuring different variables in the population of interest at a single point of time. Case study was used in this study because is a very popular form of qualitative analysis and involves a careful and complete observation of a social unit

3.3 Target Population

Ogula (2005), population refers to any group of institutions, people or objects that have common characteristics. The target populations of the study were business owners, bankers, workers from industries and companies, small businessman as well as citizens from Moshi Municipality.

3.4 Description of the Sample and Sampling Procedure

3.4.1 Sample Size

This refers to the number of items to be selected from the universe to constitute a sample (Kothari, 2004). The researcher used a sample size of 100 respondents in Moshi Municipality.

3.4.2 Sampling procedure

Sampling is a procedure, process or technique of choosing a sub-group from a population to participate in the study Ogula (2005). It is the process of selecting a number of individuals for a study in such a way that the individuals selected represent the large group from which they will be selected. Simple random sampling and purposive sampling was used to select the respondents

3.4.3 Purposive Sampling

In this study researcher was used this method to collect information from the business owners in industries and private companies in Moshi Municipality. This method was adopted because the respondents possess the qualities that researcher want to collect information.

3.4.4 Simple Random Sampling

This is the techniques in which each member of the population has equal chance of being selected as subject. The study used lottery method to do simple random sampling whereby each member of subject in the field of study is given a unique number which are then was collected and placed in a hat. The researcher thoroughly mixed the numbers and blindly picks the numbers that was used as study sample. This method is good because it provides equal chances for every individual to be selected during sampling. The researcher also used this technique to collect information from workers and citizens because it is simple and take short time.

3.5 Description of Data Collection Instruments Questionnaire

A questionnaire is a written instrument used to obtain information from study subjects. This method of data collections is suitable because the large information will be collected in short period of time and in a relatively low cost. The researcher

used this method to collect the information from workers, small business owners and citizens in Moshi Municipal. The questionnaire is likely to be a less expensive procedure as it is simply mailed to the respondents with a minimum of explanation.

Interview Guide

An interview is typically a face-to-face conversation between a researcher and a participant involving a transfer of information to the interviewer (Creswell, 2012). The researcher used interview guide questions to collect information from the business owners from industries, banks and companies within Moshi Municipal. The researcher used this instrument because the respondents contain the qualities that are important to the researcher for collection of reliable information for study.

3.6 Validity and Reliability of Research Instrument

Validity

The validity of the research instrument is the degree to which an instrument measure what it is supposed to measure. When conclusions are true the research is valid. In order for the research to be valid what is described recognized by research participants, experts from Mwenge University reviewed the research instruments to check the relevance and tools for language clarify. The experts then given comments which accommodated by the researcher to improve the instruments before giving for data collection.

Reliability

Reliability of research instrument is a consistence and replication over a time, over instrument and over group of respondents. It is concerned with precise and accuracy. For reliability of research instruments the researcher avoided errors that are caused by administration of the instruments. The instruments are reliable since they provided nearly the same result for which when treated repeatedly under the same conditions. The result collected from one respondent at a time provided results that are close to one another as that of one from different context.

3.7 Description of Data Collection Procedures

A data collection procedure involved approval from the supervisor and permission from the administration. After arriving to the field area, the researcher was

introduced to the participants, explained the purpose of the study and ensures confidentiality and anonymity of the participants. Then the instrument for data collection in this study was given to the required respondents.

3.8 Description of Data Analysis Procedure

After collecting quantitative data, researcher used to make data entry using excel program and finally analyze data in form of graphs and tables. Qualitative data were recorded in form narration and quotations from the respondents. The data was analysed in frequency and percentage under the aid of a computer program Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS Version 23) and presented by using tables.

3.9 Ethical Consideration

The researcher considered the following ethical research issues.

- i. Confidentiality and privacy of data that all information given by respondent through questionnaire and any other information was confidential to avoid link and no name was mentioned in this study.
- ii. The researcher informed the respondents the objectives of conducting this and is free to participate in the study.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.0 Chapter Overview

This chapter presents the result from data analysis presentation and discussion of research findings; it will cover background information of the respondent and response rate.

4.1 Basic Profile of Respondents

A total of 100 questionnaires were produced and administered to the sampled respondents, at the end of data collection process a total of 50 questionnaires were returned, coded and analyzed.

4.2 Age of respondent

The study revealed that the respondent (40%) who were the majority were between the age of 21-25, followed by (24%) of the respondent in the age of 31 and above years, (20%) being the age 15-20 Years, and (16%) was age of 26-30 Years. This

category helped the researcher to know the exactly age that the respondent has in order to meet the objectives of this study

Figure 1: age of the respondent.

	Frequency	Percent
15-20 years	10	20
21-25 Years	19	40
26-30 Years	9	16
30 and above	12	24
Total	50	100.0

Source: Research Study (2026)

4.3. Level of Education

The researcher was interested to know the Education level of the respondents since the skills, knowledge and experience on stakeholders and competition as well as the understanding of the national growth and development, whereby 50% they have bachelor degree in different aspects such as Business administration, Entrepreneurs and others while 24% had Diploma level and 20% had certificate as well as 6% had high level of education which helped much to this study by sharing their experience, advices and skills.

Figure 2: level of education

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Certificate	10	20.00
	Diploma	12	24.00
	Bachelor	25	50.00
	Postgraduate	3	6.00
	Total	50	100.0

Source: Research Study (2026)

4.4 Gender status

Summary of the findings Out of the 50 respondents interviewed 55% were male while 45% were female making the study result more gender sensitive (See Table 4.1).

Figure 3: Gender status

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Male	28	55.00
	Female	22	45.00
	Total	50	100.0

Source: Research Study (2026)

4.5. Marital status

The researcher was interested to know the marital status of respondents; Table 4.4 shows that 60% of respondents were single, whereas 40% were married.

Figure 5: Marital Status

Marital Status		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Single	30	60.00
	Married	20	40.00
	Total	50	100.0

Source: Research Study (2026)

4.6. Involvement of private stakeholder

The researcher intended to know involvement of private stakeholders in competition to enhancing national growth and development. Through different criteria the research had different aspects of private stakeholder involvement such as attract visitors for a temporary stay to participate in tourism related activities, increase number of travelers, stimulate globalization, building better business enabling environments, responsible for the marketing of an identifiable destination, contracting laws and providing the infrastructures essential for business. Whereby 86% of the respondent agreed on these aspects as involvement of private stakeholder in competition to enhancing national growth and development. Also 12 disagreed on these aspects.

Figure 6: Involvement of private stakeholder

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Agree	44	86.00
	Disagree	6	12.00
	Total	50	100.0

Source: Research Study (2026)

4.7. Impacts of private stakeholders

The researcher identified the impacts of private stakeholders in national growth and development as follows;

- i. Engine of economic growth. The respondent 10% said that the stakeholders act as the engine to the economic growth through creation of various products or services, as well as through paying Taxes which contributes to growth of revenues.
- ii. Competition: This makes the products and services to be more competitive in the same industry. Whereby 20% of the respondents said that competition is the impact of stakeholders in national growth.
- iii. Provision of social services. Private stakeholders provide social services to societies such as education, health and insurance and building of infrastructures, 16% of the respondents said that private stakeholders in Moshi Municipal has led to availability of social services.
- iv. Creation of heavy projects: The stakeholders provide funds which can lead to heavy projects and opportunities of investments. In Moshi Municipal, 40% respondents said that the presence of private stakeholders leads to heavy projects or investments opportunities.
- v. Stimulate smooth trade: The stakeholder involvement in different activities leads to smooth trade activities. 12% of the respondents said that having private stakeholders in business environment helps in trade activities in the current market industry.

vi. **Source: Research Study (2026)Figure 7: Impacts of private stakeholders.**

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Engine of economic growth	5	10.00
	Competition	10	20.00
	Provision social services	8	16.00
	Creation of heavy projects	21	40.00
	Stimulate smooth trade	6	12.00
	Total	50	98.0

Source: Research Study (2026)

4.8. Factors that hinder private stakeholders in competition in enhancing national growth.

According to the respondent information the following factors that hinder private stakeholders in competition in enhancing national growth;

- i) They are not involved in decision making. The private stakeholder has no right to make decisions in the organization. Through this study 16% of the respondent said that, and this can hinder creativity or innovation of stakeholders on different aspects.
- ii) Political ideology: Different political ideology that occurs within the country leads to less involvement of private stakeholder in the current competition environment. This study identified that 29% of the respondent suggested that there should be good ideologies which can make the private stakeholders to engage more in business activity
- iii) Tax and regulations. Heavy taxes levied to private stakeholder hinder the engagement of the stakeholder in business which may reduce the growth of the national. 29% of the study ‘respondents said that the government should create conducive taxes and regulation which can ensure better engagement of private stakeholders
- iv) Failure to build better business enabling environments. The government should make the conducive environment whereby the private stakeholder can work better, whereby 16% of the respondent said that the inadequate business environment leads to poor engagement of the stakeholders in the competitive environments.

Figure 8: factors that hinder private stakeholders in competition in enhancing national growth

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	They are not involved in decision making	8	15.7
	Political ideology	15	29.4
	fail to addressing constraints to growth in specific markets	4	7.8
	Tax	15	29.4
	Failure to build better business enabling environments	8	15.7
	Total	50	98.0
Missing	System	1	2.0
Total		51	100.0

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